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Effect of Thermal History On The Thermal Expansion Behavior Of SiC Whisker Reinforced Aluminum Composite

M. Hu, W. D. Fei and C. K. Yao

School of Materials Science and Engineering, P. O. Box 433, Harbin Institute of Technology, Harbin 150001, P. R. China

ABSTRACT

The thermal expansion behaviors of SiC whisker reinforced pure aluminum composites cooled down from 580°C with lower and higher cooling rates were studied in the present research. The results indicated that the thermal expansion behaviors of composite were affected by the cooling rate greatly. To explain the results, the microstructure and internal stress of the composite were examined by transmission electronic microscope and X-ray diffraction, respectively. The dislocation density and internal stress in slowly cooled composite are lower than these in fast cooled (water quenched) composite. The analysis suggested that the coefficient of thermal expansion is closely related to the change rate of internal stress and the dislocation density of matrix of the composite. The changing tendencies of internal stress in composites with different microstructures and internal stresses on heating were also analyzed.

I. INTRODUCTION

Silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composite (SiCw/Al) exhibits significant improvement in physical and mechanical properties compared with unreinforced aluminum alloys [1], such as in strength, modulus, fatigue resistance, tribological properties. In addition, it also has high thermal conductivity and low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE). Because of excellent properties of SiCw/Al composite, it has been considered as a high potential material in some areas, such as aerospace and electronic industries, although the cost of the composite is higher. As structural components with temperature variable, the materials used must have good performance including high mechanical properties, lower and stable CTE and so on. Therefore, it is very important to study the thermal expansion behaviors of the composite.

Many researches have been done for the CTE of particulate and long fiber reinforced aluminum composites [2-6], and many theoretical models such as Turner's [7], Kerner's [8] and Schapery's [9] models were employed to discuss the thermal expansion behaviors of composites. But, few studies

are concerned with the thermal expansion behaviors of whisker reinforced aluminum composites [10]. As well known, the CTE of metal matrix composite is closely related to the thermal mismatch stress in composites. All metal matrix composites contain thermal mismatch stress because of the large difference between the CTEs of the ceramic reinforcements and aluminum matrixes. Masutti et al [11] indicated that the residual stress and yield strength at elevated temperature of continuously reinforced aluminum composite could be measured by thermal expansion curves. Unfortunately, few researches have been reported on the influences of microstructure and residual stress on the thermal expansion behavior of SiCw/Al composite.

In the present research, the microstructure and residual stress of SiCw/Al composite were changed by different heat treatments, and their effects on the thermal expansion behaviors of the composite were analyzed.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The SiCw/Al composite used was fabricated by squeeze casting technique with the whisker volume fraction of 18%, and the matrix was pure aluminum.

Before CTE measurements, the specimens were treated with two techniques, the one was annealed at 580°C for 2 hours then cooled to room temperature with lower cooling rate of 1°C/min, the other was annealed at 580°C for 2 hours then quenched to water with room temperature. The former and the latter are referred slowly cooled and quenched composite in the paper. The microstructures of the composites after different heat treatments were investigated by transmission electronic microscope (TEM) on a Philips CM-12 TEM with the operating voltage of 120kV. The Specimens for TEM observation were thinned by ion milling with cooling stage in order to keep the specimen temperature approached room temperature during ion milling. The residual internal stresses in the specimens for different heat treatments were estimated by X-ray diffraction (XRD) method on thin plate specimens on a Philips X' Pert diffractometer [12].

The specimens with the dimension of $5\text{mm}\times 18\text{mm}$ for CTE measurement were cut from the cylindrical composite ingot, and all center distances between the specimens and composite ingot cylinder are same. The CTE curves were measured using a Netzsch DIL402C Dilatometer with the heating rate of 2.5°C/min and 8°C/min, respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure and internal stress

The TEM images of the microstructures of composites subjected to different heat treatments are shown in Fig. 3, all images were taken with the operation vector of $\mathbf{g} = \langle 111 \rangle$. It can be found that the dislocation densities and states in the two specimens are quite different. In the matrix of slowly cooled specimen, the dislocation density is lower, and the dominant feature of the dislocation state is

straight, as shown in Fig. 1 (a). However, the very densified dislocations can be seen in the matrix of quenched specimens as shown in Fig. 1 (b), and almost dislocations are tangled. It can be suggested that the strength of quenched specimen is higher than that of slowly cooled specimen due to high densified dislocation strengthening.

Because of the large difference between the CTEs of SiC whisker and aluminum, the internal stress is introduced in the composite on cooling from 580°C. At higher temperature, the yield strength of matrix is very low, which results in the relaxation of internal stress and plastic deformation of matrix. The plastic deformation may cause the dislocation generation in the matrix of composite. Otherwise, if the cooling rate is enough slow, the recovery process of matrix can also take place, which leads to the annihilation of dislocation. Therefore, the dislocation state in the matrix is controlled by the competition between the dislocation generation and annihilation processes. When the composite is cooled down from higher temperature with lower cooling rate (e.g. 1°C/min), the recovery process can be carried out enough and the dislocation annihilation rate may be greater than dislocation generation rate. If the composite is cooled down from higher temperature with higher cooling rate (e.g. quenching), the dislocation annihilation takes place very difficulty, which suggests that the dislocation generation rate is higher than annihilation rate. On the basis above analysis, it is easy to understand that the dislocation density in the slowly cooled specimen is lower than that in the quenched specimen. Because of heavily plastic deformation, the matrix in the quenched composite is intensively work hardening and the tangle state of dislocation is obtained.

The average internal stresses in the matrix of composites subjected to different heat treatments are listed in Table 1. The internal stress in the matrix of composite is tensile, which is agreement with the previous researches [13-15]. It can be found that the internal stress in the slowly cooled specimen is lower than that in the quenched specimen.

Table 1 Average internal stress in the matrix of composite

	Slowly cooled specimen	Quenched specimen
Internal stress	100 MPa	150MPa

As the yield strength of matrix at higher temperature is lower, the internal stress resulting from the great difference of CTE between SiC whisker and aluminum may be relaxed by plastic deformation of matrix at higher temperature on cooling. Only do the yield strength of matrix is higher than internal strength at a certain temperature, T_c , the internal stress can be kept below the temperature of T_c on cooling. It is obvious that the lower the yield strength of matrix, the lower the T_c , and the lower the residual internal stress at room temperature. When the composite is quenched from high temperature, the dislocation in matrix can not be recovered enough, and the higher strength of the matrix is obtained. For slowly cooled composite, the dislocations in the matrix are recovered at higher temperature on cooling due to lower cooling rate, which results in the lower yield strength of matrix. Therefore, the internal stress in quenched composite is higher than that in slowly cooled

composite.

3.2 Thermal expansion behavior

The relative elongation and CTE are defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{e}_T = \frac{\Delta l}{l_0} = \frac{l - l_0}{l_0} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{dl}{ldT} \quad (2)$$

where, \mathbf{e}_T is the relative elongation, l_0 the original length of the specimen, l the length of specimen at temperature T , \mathbf{a} the CTE. The relative elongation and CTE of pure aluminum as functions of temperature are given in Fig. 2. It can be seen that the CTE of pure aluminum increases slightly with temperature increasing. Comparing Fig. 2 (a) with (b), it can be found that the CTE of pure aluminum with higher heating rate is greater than that with lower heating rate on the CTE measurement.

The relationship between CTE and T for pure aluminum is approximately linear, which can be written as

$$\mathbf{a}_m = A + BT \quad (3)$$

where, \mathbf{a}_m is the CTE of pure aluminum, A and B are constants depended on heating rate of CTE measurement, A is about $24.99 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$ for the heating rate of $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $23.9 \times 10^{-6} \text{K}^{-1}$ for the heating rate of $8^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, B is about $0.64 \times 10^{-8} \text{K}^{-2}$ for the heating rate of $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $1.29 \times 10^{-8} \text{K}^{-2}$ for the heating rate of $8^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

The curves of relative elongation and CTE vs temperature for quenched composite are shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the CTE curve of quenched composite is quite different from that of pure aluminum. When the heating rate is $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in the measurement of CTE, the CTE vs temperature curve has a minimum peak at about 110°C , and a maximum peak at about 245°C , as shown in Fig. 3(a). However, when the heating rate is $8^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, only one maximum peak in the CTE vs temperature curve can be found, as shown in Fig. 5(b). As observed for pure aluminum specimen, the CTE of quenched composite with heating rate of $8^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ is greater than that with heating rate of $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

The curves of relative elongation and CTE vs temperature for slowly cooled composite are shown in Fig. 4. An obvious feature in slowly cooled composite is that no clear maximum peak can be found in CTE vs temperature curves. When the heating rate is $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in CTE measurement, there exists a minimum peak in CTE vs temperature of slowly cooled composite (shown in Fig. 4, a), but it is smaller than that of quenched composite. Except for the weaker minimum peak in CTE vs temperature curve with cooling rate of $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, the CTEs of slowly cooled composite with the heating rates of both $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $8^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ increase with temperature increasing. It can also be

seen that the CTE of slowly cooled composite with heating rate of 8°C/min is greater than that with heating rate of 2.5°C/min.

Comparing Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, one can find that the CTE of SiCw/Al composite is very sensitive to the thermal route of the composite. The obvious difference of thermal expansion behavior between the quenched and slowly cooled composite suggests that the CTE of SiCw/Al composite can be controlled by heat treatment. Our research [16] indicated that the mechanical properties of SiCw/Al composite is also dependent on heat treatment, so to understand the mechanism of CTE depending on treatment is very important for the optimization of the composite properties.

3.3 Discussion

Although some theoretical model [7-9] have been used to analyze the CTEs of metal matrix composites, it is very difficult to predict exactly the CTE of whisker reinforced aluminum composite with different microstructure and internal stress. The following analysis is simplified to explain the effects of internal stress and microstructure on the CTE of composite. The high bonding strength of the interface between SiC whisker and aluminum alloy in SiCw/Al composite has been confirmed [17,18], so it is assumed that no sliding at interface in SiCw/Al composite takes place during the composite heating for CTE measurement. If shear deformation is neglected, the changing rate of internal stress on heating may be expressed as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{v_m}{K_m} d\mathbf{s}_m &= dv_m - v_m \mathbf{b}_m dT \\ \frac{v_f}{K_f} d\mathbf{s}_f &= dv_f - v_f \mathbf{b}_f dT \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where, \mathbf{s}_m and \mathbf{s}_f are the internal stresses of matrix and whisker in composite, v_m and v_f the volumes of matrix and whisker, K_m and K_f the bulk moduli of matrix and whisker, \mathbf{b}_m and \mathbf{b}_f the bulk CTE of matrix and whisker, dv_m and dv_f the changes of matrix and whisker volume in the temperature interval from T to $T + dT$ in composite. From Equ. 4, we can obtain that

$$K_f dv_m + K_f dv_f = (K_f v_m \mathbf{b}_m + K_f v_f \mathbf{b}_f) dT + v_m d\mathbf{s}_m + v_f d\mathbf{s}_f \quad (5)$$

If we neglect small quantities, as proved in Appendix I, the following equation can be obtained:

$$\mathbf{a}_c = \mathbf{a}_M + \frac{v_m}{3} \left(\frac{1}{K_m} - \frac{1}{K_f} \right) \frac{d\mathbf{s}_m}{dT} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\mathbf{a}_M = V_m \mathbf{a}_m + V_f \mathbf{a}_f \quad (7)$$

where, V_m and V_f are the volume fractions of matrix and whisker, \mathbf{a}_m and \mathbf{a}_f the CTEs of pure aluminum and SiC whisker, and \mathbf{a}_c the CTE of composite. Because $K_m < K_f$, that \mathbf{a}_c is greater or smaller than \mathbf{a}_m depends on the sign of $d\mathbf{s}_m/dT$. On the basis of above simplified analysis, the

difference between the thermal expansion behaviors of quenched and slowly cooled composites may be understood as follows.

On the one hand, the internal stresses in both quenched and slowly cooled composite are tensile in matrix, as shown in Table 1. When composites were heated, the expansion of matrix is greater than that of whisker, the tensile internal stress in matrix can be decreased, which leads to $d\mathbf{s}_m/dT < 0$, and $a_c < a_M$. This relaxation mechanism is named as *thermal elastic relaxation*. With the temperature increasing further during the CTE measurements, the tensile internal stress in matrix may be changed to compressive stress. If the internal stress decreases monotonously, $d\mathbf{s}_m/dT < 0$, and $a_c < a_M$.

On the other hand, because the yield strength of matrix decreases with the temperature increasing, the internal stress may be relaxed by the plastic deformation of matrix [19, 20]. This relaxation mechanism of internal stress is named as *thermal plastic relaxation*. For random whisker reinforced aluminum composite, the internal stress is short range [17], the plastic deformations in different zones are also random, so the plastic deformation itself caused by thermal plastic relaxation can not lead to the change of total volume of composite. However, the relaxation of internal stress leads to the decrease of elastic internal stress, which can cause the change of CTE of the composite according to Eq. 6. One can find that the relaxation of tensile stress in the matrix causes the decrease of CTE of the composite, but the relaxation of compressive stress in the matrix causes the enhancement of CTE of the composite.

As shown in Table 1, much internal stress exists in the quenched composite. When the composite is heated to a certain temperature, the tensile yield strength of matrix decreases and the internal stress may exceed it, the thermal plastic relaxation may take place, which results in the additional decrease of the CTE of composite. The minimum peaks (shown in Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 4(a)) in CTE vs temperature curves with the heating rate of $2.5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ for both quenched and slowly cooled composite are corresponding to the thermal plastic relaxation of tensile stress in matrix. As the internal stress in slowly cooled composite is lower than that in quenched one, the quantity of tensile internal stress relaxation caused by matrix plastic deformation in the slowly cooled composite is smaller than that in quenched composite. Therefore the minimum peak in the CTE curves of slowly cooled composite is smaller than that of quenched composite (shown in Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 4(a)). When the heating rate is faster in CTE measurement ($8^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in the present study), the plastic deformation can not take place greatly at lower temperature because of short stay time of the specimen in a certain temperature interval. For this reason, the minimum peak can not be seen in the CTE curves (shown Fig. 3(b) and Fig. 4(b)).

As mentioned above, the internal stress in matrix may be changed from tensile stress to compressive one with the temperature continuously increasing. As the plastic relaxation of tensile internal stress in matrix, the compressive internal stress in matrix can also be relaxed by plastic deformation of matrix, which leads to the positive value of $d\mathbf{s}_m/dT$ and results in the CTE increasing.

For the quenched composite, the dislocation density and yield strength of the composite are higher, the compressive internal stress in the matrix at higher temperature may accumulate quite high value before the compressive stress relaxation by matrix plastic deformation. The maximum peak (see Fig. 3) in CTE curves of quenched composite suggests that the initially compressive plastic deformation in matrix takes place very fast, and positive $d\mathbf{s}_m/dT$ increases sharply. After the event of sharp plastic deformation of matrix, the compressive internal stress decreases more and more slowly, which causes the positive value of $d\mathbf{s}_m/dT$ decreases and the maximum peak presents in the CTE curves for quenched composite. For the slowly cooled composite, the dislocation density and compressive yield strength is lower, the compressive internal stress can not be accumulated enough high value, so the maximum peak disappears in the CTE curve.

According to above analysis, because the CTE of composite is dependent on the relaxation of internal stress of SiCw/Al composite, the changing tendency of the internal stress in the matrix of composite can be discussed. The changing tendencies of internal stress in quenched and slowly cooled composites are schematically illustrated in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, respectively. In the figures, the \mathbf{a}_M is determined using Eq. 3 and 7, and assuming the CTE of SiC whisker is a constant in the temperature interval of the CTE measurements and its value is $4.5 \times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$ [2].

For the quenched composite (see Fig. 5), the CTE from point A to D in CTE curve is smaller than \mathbf{a}_M means $d\mathbf{s}_m/dT < 0$. As the CTE from point B to C is a minimum peak, the corresponding internal stress from point decreases rapidly, which suggests that relaxation of tensile internal stress in the matrix may be mainly thermal plastic relaxation in the this temperature interval. From point C to D, the internal stress in the matrix becomes compressive and its absolute value increases with temperature increasing. At point D, the absolute value of compressive internal stress reaches the maximum value and $d\mathbf{s}_m/dT = 0$, which results in the CTE of the composite is equal to \mathbf{a}_M . Because the temperature is so high and the compressive yield strength is so low at point D that a lot of plastic deformation in matrix takes place in the temperature interval from point E to F. The rapid decrease of the absolute value of compressive internal stress in matrix causes $d\mathbf{s}_m/dT > 0$ and rapid increase of the value $d\mathbf{s}_m/dT$. With the temperature increases from point E to F, the internal compressive decreases gradually due to thermal plastic relaxation mainly. Therefore, the maximum peaks in the CTE curves can be obtained.

For slowly cooled composite, the changing tendency of internal stress in the matrix of composite can also be analyzed (as shown in Fig.6) using the similar point of view in the above analysis. Because of lower yield strength and dislocation density in slowly cooled composite, the absolute compressive stress in matrix can not be accumulated to a higher value and no rapid relaxation of internal compressive stress in the matrix with the mechanism of thermal plastic relaxation takes place. Therefore, no maximum peak in slowly cooled composite can be observed, and the CTE of the composite from point D to E in Fig. 6 increases gradually.

IV. SUMMARY

The dislocation density and internal stress of SiCw/Al composite after annealing at 580°C are affected by cooling rate. The dislocation and internal stress in the quenched composite are higher than that in slowly cooled composite. The differences of internal stresses and dislocation densities between the quenched and slowly cooled composites are considered as the differences of internal relaxation and degree of recovery on cooling of annealing treatment between the two composite.

The thermal expansion behavior of quenched SiCw/Al composite is quite different from that of slowly cooled composite. The CTE vs temperature curve of quenched composite has a minimum and a maximum peak, but no maximum peak can be found for slowly cooled composite.

A simplified analysis indicated that the CTE of composite depends on relaxation behavior of internal stress on heating for the CTE experiments; consequently, the microstructure and internal stress in matrix have great effects on the thermal expansion behaviors of SiCw/Al composite.

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1 TEM micrographs of *a* slowly cooled and *b* quenched SiCw/Al composite, taken with the operation vector of $\mathbf{g} = \langle 111 \rangle$

Fig. 2 Curves of relative elongation and CTE vs temperature for the pure aluminum with the heating rate of *a* 2.5 °C/min and *b* 8 °C/min

Fig. 3 Curves of relative elongation and CTE vs temperature for the quenched SiCw/Al composite with the heating rate of *a* 2.5 °C/min and *b* 8 °C/min

Fig. 4 Curves of relative elongation and CTE vs temperature for the slowly cooled SiCw/A composite with the heating rate of a 2.5°C/min and b 8°C/min

Fig.5 Schematic diagram of the changing tendency of internal stress in the quenched SiCw/Al composite

Fig. 6 Schematic diagram of the changing tendency of internal stress in the slowly cooled SiCw/Al composite

